

GEO MORPHOMETRY
PERUGIA ITALY

2025
JUNE 9-13

A qualitative comparison of corrected global DEMs

Maarten Pronk

Hydrology Software
Deltares

Delft, the Netherlands
maarten.pronk@deltares.nl

Hugo Ledoux

Urban Data Science
Delft University of Technology

Delft, the Netherlands
h.ledoux@tudelft.nl

Marieke Eleveld

Data Science, Water quality
Deltares

Delft, the Netherlands
marieke.eleveld@deltares.nl

Abstract— Over the past few years, several attempts have been made to derive a bare-earth model from the CopernicusDEM GLO-30 dataset, yielding FABDEM, DiluviumDEM, CoastalDEM (from version 3 onwards), and DeltaDTM (by the authors). These “urban and vegetation corrected” datasets have been quantitatively compared with auxiliary datasets, demonstrating differences in the order of decimeters in terms of vertical accuracy. More recently, the accuracy of the parameters derived from these DEMs has also been evaluated. However, despite being based on the same source dataset and using similar secondary datasets—such as ICESat-2 and GEDI—the derived datasets differ in their applied methods and resulting formats. In this study, we qualitatively investigate these differences between datasets. We assess whether new artefacts are introduced in the corrected datasets, assess whether original CopernicusDEM artefacts have been corrected, and examine the tile size, compression method, license, source code, and distribution method of the corrected datasets. We find that datasets using machine learning have uncorrected patch sized artefacts, while DeltaDTM exhibits “bomb-craters” within individual tiles due to unfiltered outliers in ICESat-2 data. In all datasets, most of the original CopernicusDEM artefacts remain uncorrected. Additionally, all datasets use slightly different file formats and often resample CopernicusDEM to different tiling schemes. None of these methodological choices or datasets can be deemed the “best,” although some are less optimal. We conclude that all datasets have room for improvement, and future versions will likely benefit from adopting strategies used in creation of the other datasets.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, several attempts have been made to derive a bare-earth model from the CopernicusDEM GLO-30 [1] dataset. These include FABDEM [2], DiluviumDEM [3], CoastalDEM (from version 3 onwards) [4, 5], and DeltaDTM [6, 7]. All datasets attempt to remove urban and vegetation biases present in the CopernicusDEM source dataset—itsself a surface model (DSM)—to arrive at a terrain model (DTM). Of these “corrected” datasets, only FABDEM is available globally, the others are *coastal* datasets, only available up to some meters above sea-level.

Most datasets (Table 1) make use of machine learning to regress the elevations of CopernicusDEM, with two opting for a Random Forest (RF) models. Only CoastalDEM uses a Neural Network, moving to a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) in v3.0. DeltaDTM is the odd one out, with applying a custom heuristic scheme of bias correction, filtering and interpolation. DiluviumDEM and DeltaDTM share an open CC-BY license, whereas FABDEM and CoastalDEM have a restricted license, with free use only for research purposes.

TABLE I. OVERVIEW OF DATASETS

Name	Year of release	Current version	Scope	Method	License
FABDEM	2022	1.2	Global	RF	Restricted
CoastalDEM	2018	3.0	Coastal, up to 120 m	CNN	Restricted
DiluviumDEM	2023	1.0	Coastal, up to 80 m	RF	Open
DeltaDTM	2024	1.1.1	Coastal, up to 30 m (initially up to 10 m)	Heuristic	Open

More recent datasets (or version updates thereof) tend to be more vertically accurate by their own metrics. Third party comparisons have shown that these datasets improve on the elevation accuracy of CopernicusDEM, but less so on derived metrics, such as slope or flow accumulation [8].

Qualitative differences, such as the details on distribution of the datasets, or the effect the different methodologies have on elevation (corrections), have been studied less. In this study we aim to improve that, as these qualities are not only essential for ease of use and adoption for end users, but also for the developers of these datasets. We want to be upfront about our involvement as authors of DeltaDTM and emphasize our impartiality in this reproduceable comparison. Our goal is to improve current and future global terrain models.

II. RESULTS

A. Elevation inconsistencies

Several artefacts exist in CopernicusDEM itself, often from the underlying radar processing, such as radar shadows. Each new release of CopernicusDEM (currently at the 9th release of 2024 1, © DLR e.V. 2010–2014 and © Airbus Defence and Space GmbH 2014–2018 provided under COPERNICUS by the European Union and ESA; all rights reserved) improves on this, but several artefacts on smaller scales—such as diagonal “walls” and pits—are persistent (Fig. 1). None of the datasets improve such diagonal patterns, and only some fix the presence of pits (FABDEM, CoastalDEM, and DeltaDTM to an extent). FABDEM and CoastalDEM might have made these fixes accidentally by smoothing and resampling, respectively.

Depending on how one improves the elevations of CopernicusDEM, different terrains emerge. On larger scales these landscapes have been validated by deriving parameters such as slope or roughness, but details related to the method used to correct the elevation emerge on smaller scales. In Fig. 2 we can identify the different methods (and datasets) by the artefacts created by each of them. FABDEM introduces square artefacts of 3x3 pixels, sometimes creating larger patterns in dense tropical forests. Similarly, CoastalDEM—using a CNN—has patch-sized artefacts of 64x64 pixels where little or no correction has been applied. We assume that no ICESat-2 or GEDI data was available for such a patch.

DiluviumDEM, by regressing a single pixel at a time, creates a very rough surface, as pixels in a striped pattern are much lower than the surrounding surface. Unlike FABDEM, the resulting surface was not smoothed. Finally, DeltaDTM has so called “bomb-craters” caused by low outliers in ICESat-2, which were not filtered everywhere. This pattern is sometimes also seen in airborne-lidar processing.

Figure 1. Artefacts in CopernicusDEM. A) Diagonal “wall” of 1.5m in an otherwise flat delta. B) Pits caused by electricity poles (multiple reflections)

Figure 2. Artefacts introduced by each method: A) Square artefacts in FABDEM, starting at 3x3 pixels. B) Patch-sized 64x64 pixel artefacts in CoastalDEM. C) Very low individual pixels in a striped pattern (high roughness) in DiluviumDEM and D) Stripes (ICESat-2 tracks) of low outlier craters in DeltaDTM.

B. Formats and distribution

All datasets, like CopernicusDEM itself, distribute their files as geotiffs in 1 by 1-degree tiles. The comparisons end there however, as all datasets change the format (Table II). Indeed, most opt for a single tile size everywhere, instead of the DGED specification (different tile sizes per latitude range, with Copernicus being 3601x3601 pixels at the equator).

Except for CoastalDEM (at least the 90 m research version), all datasets cut off the single pixel row/column that overlaps with other tiles. FABDEM and DeltaDTM distribute the data as Cloud Optimized Geotiffs (COG), which includes sub-tiling and adding overviews to each tile, which requires an even tile size.

TABLE II. DISTRIBUTION FORMATS

Name	File Format	Compression	Water	Mask supplied	Tile size	Single tile size
FABDEM	COG	Deflate	Original	No	3600	Yes
CoastalDEM	Geotiff	Deflate	Original	No	1201 (90 m resolution)	Yes
DiluviumDEM	Geotiff	LZW	Original	No	3600	Yes
DeltaDTM	COG	ZSTD	Nodata	Yes	3600	No

FABDEM, DiluviumDEM and DeltaDTM can be downloaded from public data repositories without user registration. FABDEM distributes zip files containing all tiles in a 10 by 10-degree area, and DiluviumDEM does so for a 5 by 5-degree area. DeltaDTM provides zip files per continent, and CoastalDEM provides a single large zip file after registration and manual approval.

Compression options vary for the datasets, with FABDEM and CoastalDEM choosing the widely available Deflate algorithm. DiluviumDEM and DeltaDTM opt for the LZW and ZSTD algorithms respectively, to save more storage space.

Most datasets keep the elevation values for water (e.g. 0 for sea and ocean, and elevations in rivers increasing with steps of 0.5 m) in CopernicusDEM intact, with only DeltaDTM opting to replace them with nodata values. DeltaDTM is also the only dataset to distribute the original mask tiles of CopernicusDEM next to the dataset.

III. DISCUSSION

While all datasets start with the same CopernicusDEM dataset, they differ considerably in their outcomes. While no single dataset (decision) can be defined as best, common patterns between datasets emerge that we would qualify as optimal here.

None of the datasets correct larger artefacts present in CopernicusDEM, but some fix the presence of pits. All datasets could be further improved by checking for artefacts introduced by their methods. DeltaDTM could reconsider using raw ICESat-2 values directly. All other datasets—based on ML—could be improved by not using the raw ML output (whether individual pixels or patches) directly, or using outputs that overlap, to prevent square-like artefacts common to these datasets.

In terms of file format, using Cloud Optimized Geotiff, but with a common algorithm such as Deflate, would optimize for (future) cloud-based workflows, and still be useable by most GISes. All datasets strip the single pixel column/row overlap of CopernicusDEM, which is required for COG. Most datasets also resample to a fixed tile size, foregoing the DGED spacing per latitude zone. While easier to handle, there is some data loss involved with resampling, and common derivatives like slope operations require awareness of the resulting non-square pixels at higher latitudes.

Masking out water values as done by DeltaDTM seems suboptimal, but we suggest that providing CopernicusDEM (water)masks (but resampled) is optimal, as users cannot otherwise identify or mask water values.

Distribution of the datasets is best done on a publicly accessible website, and in zip files spanning several degrees (tiles). It seems distribution by continent, let alone all data in a single zip, is suboptimal. We note that while FABDEM and DeltaDTM store their data as COG, a (public) cloud location where individual tiles (i.e. no zip files) can be accessed has not been advertised.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the authors of FABDEM, CoastalDEM, DiluviumDEM and DeltaDTM for their work and enabling this research by providing the datasets for research purposes.

REFERENCES

- [1] European Space Agency; Airbus. (2022). Copernicus DEM, European Space Agency. doi:[10.5270/ESA-c5d3d65](https://doi.org/10.5270/ESA-c5d3d65)
- [2] Hawker, L.; Uhe, P.; Paulo, L.; Sosa, J.; Savage, J.; Sampson, C.; Neal, J. (2022). A 30 m global map of elevation with forests and buildings removed, *Environmental Research Letters*, Vol. 17, No. 2, 024016. doi:[10.1088/1748-9326/ac4d4f](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac4d4f)
- [3] Dusseau, D.; Zobel, Z.; Schwalm, C. R. (2023). DiluviumDEM: Enhanced accuracy in global coastal digital elevation models, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Vol. 298, 113812. doi:[10.1016/j.rse.2023.113812](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2023.113812)
- [4] Kulp, S. A.; Strauss, B. H. (2018). CoastalDEM: A global coastal digital elevation model improved from SRTM using a neural network, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Vol. 206, 231–239. doi:[10/gc9n4s](https://doi.org/10/gc9n4s)
- [5] Kulp, S. A.; Strauss, B. H. (2024). *CoastalDEM v3.0: Improving fully global coastal elevation predictions through a convolutional neural network and multi-source DEM fusion* Climate Central
- [6] Pronk, M.; Hooijer, A.; Eilander, D.; Haag, A.; de Jong, T.; Vousdoukas, M.; Vernimmen, R.; Ledoux, H.; Eleveld, M. (2024). DeltaDTM: A global coastal digital terrain model, *Scientific Data*, Vol. 11, No. 1, 273. doi:[10.1038/s41597-024-03091-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03091-9)
- [7] Pronk, M. (2024, December 12). DeltaDTM: A global coastal digital terrain model, 4TU.ResearchData. doi:[10.4121/21997565](https://doi.org/10.4121/21997565)
- [8] Guth, P. L.; Trevisani, S.; Grohmann, C. H.; Lindsay, J.; Gesch, D.; Hawker, L.; Bielski, C. (2024). Ranking of 10 Global One-Arc-Second DEMs Reveals Limitations in Terrain Morphology Representation, *Remote Sensing*, Vol. 16, No. 17, 3273. doi:[10.3390/rs16173273](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16173273)